

LINKING ALGORITHM OF BIBLIOGRAPHICAL DATABASE

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Abstract: This article discusses the process of searching for information in the bibliographic database. Here developed an algorithm for obtaining results according to certain characteristics of the information related to the sought record.

Keywords: bibliographic record, electronic catalog, information-library systems, information-resource centers, full text, Electronic Library, automated information-library systems, bibliographic description.

Introduction

In the development of information and communication technologies around the world, the issues of identification of bibliographic information of objects, the constant growth of information volumes, as well as the development of scientific research are becoming increasingly important.

In order to have complete information about the objects, it is necessary to carry out the process of identification on the objects. Objects that need to be identified can be individuals, organizations, geographic objects, and so on. Data identification allows you to automatically identify the same data in the database and leave one of them as the primary data. In particular, when it comes to publishing information available in information-library catalogs.

The process of establishing a link between authoritarian and bibliographic records within the existing Automated Information Library Systems is carried out by the cataloger. On the one hand, an expert can establish a sufficiently reliable relationship between records by attracting additional information that is not in the records themselves. To solve this problem, it is advisable to use the principles and techniques of record linkage in relation to bibliographic information. There is currently a lot of work to be done in linking records or identifying duplicate data from foreign and local authors.

There are also various systems that link records like MARLIN, TAILOR, Febrl. These systems are designed to link addresses, author information, or bibliographic information in a single line. These systems cannot be used to solve a task because they do not support working with records in MARC format.

The ability to automatically determine the relationships between records related to a particular object or concept (topic section) allows you to significantly improve the status of information retrieval in an electronic catalog. Such connections allow us to significantly increase the completeness and accuracy of the search.

The comparison function performs one of the methods of comparing text strings, which can be explicit or implicit comparison. If the data is written in more than one field at a time, each record can be selected individually or in groups. The result of the comparison may consist of the following options:

- inconsistency of data;
- lack of information;
- full or partial compatibility of data;

The result of the application of each rule is expressed in numbers, and therefore there is a transition from qualitative properties (values of text fields) to quantitative properties.

Description of the algorithm

To implement the proposed model of linking records, a link model and algorithm consisting of several functional blocks was developed. B set was taken as a database of bibliographic records containing descriptions of the literature, and as set A - as a database of authoritative records of the names of authors. The developed algorithm is also suitable for collections that have two separate bibliographic records.

There are some features in this formula of the problem. Collection B entries may contain information about more than one person at a time, ie they are co-authors of the publication. Each entry in set A is dedicated to a description of one person. Thus, the following constraint is added to the problem described above:

For an arbitrary object, there can be no more than one $\alpha(a)$ (where there are records $\alpha(a) \in A$) and $\beta(b)$ (where $\beta(b) \in B$). Thus, it is necessary and sufficient to associate this record with one and only one $\alpha(a)$ records in order to identify the person mentioned in record $\beta(b)$ [4].

The following functional blocks are directly involved in the communication process.

1. Preparation block;
2. Double entry block;
3. Double entry field comparison block;
4. Decision making block;

Preparation block - β incoming data, which allows you to transfer the next block with a detailed description.

Creating a pair of records block - Comparing an unwanted β record with each a record can be a very time consuming process. Therefore, a mechanism to reduce the number of records that perform the comparison is required. Such a mechanism is implemented in the form of a separate functional block to create a pair of records.

Double entry field comparison block - The purpose of the block is to assess whether the records match different parameters. The result of the block is a vector consisting of the results of applying the rules of comparison.

Decision block - Compatibility at the entry level does not necessarily mean explicit compliance at the field level. Creating a set of matching multiple entries into one set or a set of matching pairs is done.

In general, it should be noted that the process of checking the similarity of bibliographic records in databases is carried out by comparing the bibliographic elements with each other. However, in the absence of sufficient bibliographic elements in the database, sufficient changes are made during the comparison process. The software product to be created will be used as a part program for ARMAT ++, which will be used as an automated information-library system. The developed algorithms can be used in other software products.

Fig 1. Algorithm for searching bibliographic records.

Conclusion

Resolving this issue will automatically provide information that belongs to the author as a result. Articles written by our professors are currently available in the Scopus database, and there are some shortcomings when searching for articles related to the author. That is, these shortcomings were considered as follows:

In some cases, a bibliographic description of the author's articles is not provided. This is of course due to some changes in registration (for example, full names are written differently in different languages);

Once the system has been reviewed by the organizers, the data per author will be combined.

The intended part of the program serves to eliminate the above-mentioned shortcomings and allows you to automatically link the author's bibliographic information.

References

[1] Отле П. Библиотека, библиография, документация [Текст] : Избранные труды пионера информатики / ПольОтле. – Москва: ФАИР-ПРЕСС: Пашков Дом, 2004. – 348, [1] с.

[2] Отле П. Труды по библиотековедению. Руководство для общественных библиотек. Организация умственного труда. Руководство к администрированию [Текст] : Практ. пособие / Поль Отле; [Вступ. ст. и науч. ред. Ю. Н. Столярова]. – Москва : Либерия, 2002. – 227 с. : табл. – ISBN 5-85129-148-6.

[3] Мазов Н.А. Новые методы формирования публикационного профиля научной организации в сети науки / Н. А. Мазов, В. Н. Гуреев // Науч. И техн. б-ки. – 2013. - № 12. – С. 42-48.

[4] Manning C. D. Introduction to Information Retrieval [Electronic resource] / C. D. Manning, P. Raghavan, H. SchuËtze – Cambridge, 2009–2011.

[5] Winkler W. E. Overview of record linkage and current research directions [Electronic resource] : tech. report / W. E. Winkler ; U.S. Census Bureau, Stat. res. div. – Washington : [s. n.], 2006. – 44 p. – (RRS (Statistics #2006-2)). – URL : <http://www.census.gov/srd/papers/pdf/rrs2006-02.pdf>, free. – Tit. From the screen (usage date: 04.06.2013).

[6] Talburt J. Entity resolution and information quality / John R. Talburt. – San Francisco : Morgan Kaufmann/Elsevier, 2011. – 256 p.

[7] Needleman S. B. A general method applicable to the search for similarities in the amino acid sequences of two proteins / S. B. Needleman, C. D. Wunsch // *J. mol. biol.* – 1970. – Vol. 48, № 3. – P. 443–453.

[8] Monge A. E. The field matching problem: Algorithms and applications / A. E. Monge, C. P. Elkan // *Proc. 2nd Int. conf. on knowledge discovery and data mining (KDD-96)*, Portland, OR, USA, Aug 2–4, 1996. – Portland : AAAI Press, 1996. – P. 267–270.

[9] Cilibrasi R. Clustering by compression / R. Cilibrasi, P. M. B. Vitanyi // *IEEE. trans. on inf. theory* – 2005. – Vol. 51, № 4. – P. 1523–1545.

[10] Elfeky M. G. TAILOR: a record linkage tool box / M. G. Elfeky, A. K. Elmagarmid, V. S. Verykios // *Proc. 18th Int. conf. on data eng. (ICDE 02)*, San Jose, CA, USA, 26 Febr.–1 March, 2002. – Washington : IEEE Computer Soc., 2002. – P. 17–28.